

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF STATISTICAL LEARNING MODELS FOR SOLAR IRRADIANCE PREDICTION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the predictive quality of statistical learning models in forecasting Evaporation Pitch (EVPI), which is a critical variable to predict solar evaporation, and fulfills three major objectives: comparison of linear and nonlinear prediction methods, examine the effect of standard meteorological predictors on EVPI, and determine the most reliable and valid model for operational use. Data spanning the period 1995-2023 was sourced from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMeT), in which the predictors were minimum temperature, maximum temperature, solar radiation, and wind speed, which were all standardized to enhance comparability, and EVPI itself was not highly variable and had a fairly symmetric distribution. They were fitted to five models Multiple Linear Regression, Random Forest, Support Vector Regression linear, polynomial, and radial kernel and their performance was evaluated by Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) supported by residual diagnostics and Ljung-Box test of autocorrelation. The results reveal that Support Vector Regression using radial kernel performed better than the other models with minimum RMSE (0.02852) and MAPE (0.01640) alongside showing unbiased, homoscedastic, independent and stable residuals. The results of correlation provided weak linear relationships between the predictors and EVPI, which justifies the effectiveness of the nonlinear learning methods. Therefore, the study identifies the SVR with a radial kernel as a robust and effective approach for predicting EVPI, offering valuable support for water-resource planning, salt-harvest activities, and solar-evaporation development, especially in areas with sparse observational data where sturdy predictive models are essential

Keywords: *Evaporation Pitch, Solar Evaporation Forecasting, Meteorological Variables, Multiple Linear Regression, Random Forest Regression*

JEL Code: C45, C53, Q25, Q42.

1 INTRODUCTION

The environment and economic sustainability of Nigeria depend on energy forecasting and adoption of renewable energy. The high reliance on oil and natural gas, and the accelerated industrial growth of the country has led to an increased level of environmental pollution and strengthened the necessity to shift to a cleaner and more sustainable source of energy (Jolaosho et al., 2025). Renewable energy technologies have been of impressive momentum the world over, specifically photovoltaic (pV) solar power has witnessed a rapid increase in growth. The solar capacity now has over 1,400 GW across the world, producing over 2,000 Twh annually, which is about 7% of the global electricity production (Oscar et al., 2025). This international trend is an indication of a significant chance of Nigeria to minimize climate-related dangers and environmental harm through abandoning the usual fossil-fueling methods. The move to renewable energy, however, poses a lot of complexity in operations. In contrast to fossil fuel generation plants which are deployable on demand, renewable energy sources like wind and solar are intermittent and weather driven by nature. The output of Solar PV changes due to the cloud cover, temperature, and atmospheric conditions and presents a challenge in the maintenance of grid stability.

The abrupt decreases in solar energy may bring an imbalance between the electricity supply and demand; therefore, proper forecasting is the key to the stable operation of the electricity grid. In order to solve these challenges, there has been increased use of advanced technological solutions. The intelligent control capabilities of microgrids allow the enhanced integration of distributed renewable resources, whereas the Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) allow stabilizing the grid by storing the surplus energy and releasing it whenever it is necessary. However, the optimization of battery charging and discharging options is an important operational issue (Dillon, 2024). Solar forecasting is thus required to be accurate in order to facilitate good management of energy and grid reliability. The common forecasting methods involve physical atmospheric models, statistical models, and spatial models which make use of the geographic patterns to enhance the accuracy of prediction (Fennane et al., 2025). Although much has been done on the solar irradiance and PV energy forecasting especially with the more sophisticated machine-learning and hybrid deep-learning methods, few studies have been done on the evaporation-related indicators like the Evaporation Pitch (EVPI). The significance of this gap is particularly remarkable as measures of evaporation are applicable in the context of water-resource management, solar systems that operate on evaporation, and climate-adaptation planning.

Furthermore, much of the literature available is more concerned with predictive accuracy without a serious statistical diagnostics, model-stability, and residual-behavior testing. This shortcoming invites the current research which seeks to come up with a statistically robust and reliable forecasting model of EVPI based on long-term weather information and multicompany statistical learning models, such as Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR with multiple kernels), and Random Forest. In this regard, the aim of the study is to establish the best and trusted modelling method by established accuracy factors and diagnostic tests that will help in the successful solar energy planning and embedding within the national grid.

2 LITERATURE REVIEWS

2.1 Theoretical Literature

Studies of solar radiation, photovoltaic performance, and forecasting climate-related variables have grown substantially, using both established statistical methods as well as other modern hybrid machine-learning methods. The wider applicability of energy forecasting is demonstrated by early research: Ugwoke and Dike (2016) indicate that electricity availability

is a major factor that affects the output in industries, whereas the authors cited by Sebastian et al. (2018) state that renewable-energy misuse and carbon-emission intensity are primarily conditioned by the availability of renewable energy in Sub-Saharan Africa. Following the same policy-driven line, Onyechi and Ejiofor (2021) believe that the energy mix in Nigeria should be decarbonized, and proper solar-irradiance forecasting should be regarded as a valuable asset.

2.2 Empirical Literatures

There has been a substantial amount of recent empirical research on enhancing the accuracy of solar-radiation forecasts with hybrid and non-linear models. Ondo and Owolawi (2024) used PSO-optimized FFNN, GRNN, CFNN, and ANFIS models to predict PV current using the solar radiation and temperature data points. They find that ANFIS and CFNN perform well in low-irradiation and high-irradiation conditions respectively, which proves that PSO improves the precision of the model greatly, and seasonal variability does influence the performance of the forecast. Several studies published in 2025 extend this advancement using decomposition-based and hybrid ML frameworks. Rajasundrapandiyan et al. (2025) employed EMD, EEMD, and ML algorithms, namely, MLP, Random Forest, SVR, and Ridge regression for predicting long-term solar radiation in India. They also used 13 years of data on seven cities and discovered that EEMD-MLP obtained exceptionally high accuracy ($R \approx 0.99$), which showed that EEMD could resolve mode-mixing problems. Comparing OLS, LASSO, Ridge, tree-based, neural networks, LSTM and Random Forest in intra-hour, intra-day, and day ahead horizons, Trull et al. (2025) revealed that hybrid physical-ML models always performed better compared to time-series-only models. Other researchers look at particular systems of energy-consumption. Kachalla et al. (2025) used Decision Trees, Neural Networks, LSTM, and Random Forest to predict electric-boiler energy use in real conditions under different loads with varying load conditions, and it was shown that it is highly adaptable both in the short-run and long-run. The authors of the article Ofose et al. (2025) proposed an RL-A-LSTM hybrid photovoltaic power prediction model, where the reinforcement-learning demonstrated the significant improvement of the attention mechanisms in comparison with the traditional ML models.

Another area where hybrids of deep-learning models are prominently used is climate-variable forecasting. Elabd et al. (2025) devised a CNN-GRU-LSTM architecture to forecast weather variables in Al-Qassim province of Saudi Arabia up to the year 2050 with R²-values of over 99% in most cases. Ahmed et al. (2025) developed a hybrid predictive model of temperature and wind power based on multi-source data, with the highest R² of 98-99, which means that it is highly reliable to plan the environment long-term. Comparative studies also point to the quality of non-linear and ensemble models. In the study of Fennane et al. (2025), the authors compared LSTM, GRU and a hybrid of LSTM-GRU in real-time prediction of solar-irradiance and the hybrid model had lower errors, whereas GRU was more suitable in terms of speed in calculation at the cost of a slight decrease in accuracy. Similar findings are presented by Nguyen et al. (2025), which state that tree-based, SVM, and neural networks are always more effective than linear regressions in the prediction of solar irradiance. Abdelsattar et al. (2025) also compared 9 ML models on PV-environment meteor forecasting, and discovered that Gradient Boosting, Random Forest and XGBoost models work best in noisy and complex systems, compared to linear and single-tree models.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the quantitative, comparative modelling design is embraced to increase the accuracy of solar energy generation forecasting in Nigeria through assessing the existence of linear and non-linear machine learning algorithms. The analysis was done using a 29-year climatic time-series dataset (1995-2023) of solar radiation, maximum, and minimum

temperature, wind speed, and evaporation pitch collected by Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NiMeT). When cleaning, sorting, and preprocessing the data in Microsoft Excel, it was made consistent and devoid of any possible anomalies to be imported into R (version 4.3.4) to undergo statistical modelling. Three predictive models were discussed, which are Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR) with various kernel calibrations, and Random Forest (RF). These models were chosen in order to capture linear and non-linear learning methods. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) were used to measure the model performance to determine which model is most accurate and reliable in predicting solar irradiance. The paper is based on an area in Nigeria where precise solar energy prediction is required in the management of water resources, evaluation of solar evaporation and the wide-scale planning of the region.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This paper works on the premise that nonlinear machine learning models, including Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Random Forest (RF) have the potential to model complex and time-varying relationships between climatic variables. SVR projects the inputs into high-dimensional spaces whereas the RF combines numerous decision trees to project nonlinear interactions. Previous hydrology demonstrates the effectiveness of these models in comparison to the linear ones, although the accuracy is influenced by the quality of data and varying time conditions (Bargam et al., 2024). Using this approach to solar radiation, temperature, wind speed, and evaporation, the paper applies SVR and RF to predict EVPI. This framework warrants the comparison of MLR, SVR (linear, polynomial, radial kernels) and RF and the comparison of performance based on RMSE, MAPE, and residual diagnostics.

3.2 Model Specification

3.2.1 Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR) Model

Multivariate Linear Regression is a linear approach used to model the relationship between a dependent variable and multiple independent variables.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where; Y deduced as the predicted solar energy output (dependent variable “EVPI”), X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n is the Independent variables (temperature “TMIN and TMAX”, solar radiation “RADI”, wind speed “WINS”), β_0 is the Intercept, $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ is the Coefficients for each independent variable, ε equals the Error term (residuals). According to Bargam et al. (2024) and Sun et al. (2023), transforming equation (1) into a functional econometric equation becomes;

$$LEVPI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LTMIN + \beta_2 LTMAX + \beta_3 LRADI + \beta_4 LWINS + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

3.1.2 Random Forest Regression (RFR) Model

Random Forest Regression is an ensemble machine learning method that uses multiple decision trees to improve predictive accuracy and control overfitting (Breiman, 2001).

The Random Forest prediction is the average of the predictions from all individual decision trees:

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T h_t(X) \quad (3)$$

Where; \hat{Y} = Predicted solar energy output (LEVPI), T = Total number of decision trees in the forest, $h_t(X)$ = Prediction from the t^{th} decision tree, X = Input vector of features (LTMIN, LTMAX, LRADI and LWINS). Each decision tree h_t is trained on a random subset of the data and a random subset of features, enhancing model generalization.

3.1.3 Support Vector Regression (SVR) Model

SVR is a supervised learning model capable of capturing nonlinear relationships. It attempts to fit the best function $f(x)$ within a tolerance level.

$$f(x) = \langle w, x \rangle + b \quad (4)$$

Subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} y_i - \langle w, x_i \rangle - b &\leq \varepsilon + \xi_i \\ \langle w, x_i \rangle + b - y_i &\leq \varepsilon + \xi_i^* \\ \xi_i, \xi_i^* &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

The optimization problem is expressed as:

$$\min \left(\frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n (\xi_i + \xi_i^*) \right) \tag{5}$$

Following Dewi and Chen (2019), the kernel functions adopted in this study are:

Linear $k(x_n, x) = x_n^T x + c$, **Polynomial** $k(x_n, x) = (\alpha x_n^T x + c)^d$, **Radial Basis** and

$k(x_n, x) = \exp\left(-\frac{\|x_n - x\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$ with basic statistical function given as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{n=1}^N (\beta_n - \beta_n^*) k(x_n, x) + b \tag{6}$$

Where, $f(x)$ deduced the Linear function, $\langle w, x \rangle$ as the Inner product (dot product) between weight vector (w) and input vector (x), $\frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2$ is the Regularization term controlling model complexity, C is the Penalty parameter balancing margin size and error, $\xi_i + \xi_i^*$ is Slack variables for handling misclassification or errors, $\beta_n - \beta_n^*$ is the Lagrange multipliers associated with each sample, $k(x_n, x)$ is the kernel function, b is the bias term, N deduced the number of training samples.

3.2 MODEL EVALUATION METRICS

Unstandardized measures of predictive performance are a significant drawback when attempting to make comparisons between models in a consistent and objective way. To deal with this, the current research uses two commonly accepted measures of evaluation. The forecasting accuracy of the Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR), Support Vector Regression (SVR), and Random Forest Regression (RFR) have been compared. Two error measures were used in the analysis, including Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). When combined, the metrics will give a holistic evaluation of prediction accuracy by covering various aspects of forecasting errors (Makridakis et al., 1998). The error values are presented in the following form;

3.2.1 Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n e(t)^2} \tag{7}$$

RMSE penalizes large errors, making it sensitive to outliers in the dataset.

3.2.2 Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n \left| \frac{X_{real,t} - X_{pred,t}}{X_{real,t}} \right| \tag{8}$$

MAPE provides error as a percentage, making it easier to interpret across different scales. Here; $e(t) = X_{real,t} - X_{pred,t}$, $X_{real,t}$ is the actual (real) value at time t , $X_{pred,t}$ is the predicted value at time t , n is the total number of observations. These evaluation criteria are widely used in time series forecasting literature due to their interpretability and reliability.

3.3 DIAGNOSTIC TESTS

3.3.1 Absolute Prediction Errors (APE)

The absolute prediction error measures the magnitude of deviation between observed values and predicted values (Makridakis et al., 1998).

$$APE_i = |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \tag{9}$$

3.3.2 Residuals and Residual Diagnostic

The residual is the difference between observed and predicted values.

$$e_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i \tag{10}$$

3.3.3 Residual Diagnostics with Confidence Bands

Confidence bands give an interval around the residuals to assess if the model fits within an acceptable error margin. For each predicted value \hat{y}_i , the confidence interval for the residual is expressed as;

$$C.I_i = \hat{y}_i \pm Z_{\alpha/2} \cdot \hat{\sigma} \tag{11}$$

Where, y_i is expressed as the actual observed value, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value, e_i is the residual for the i^{th} observation, APE_i deduced the absolute prediction error for the i^{th} observation, $\hat{\sigma}$ shows the estimated standard deviation of the residuals, and $C.I_i$ is the confidence band for the i^{th} residual.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS ON FINDINGS

The results of the comparative analysis of statistical learning models for solar irradiance prediction in the studied area are presented and interpreted in the following figures.

4.1 Density Curves of Standardized Predictor Variables

Figure 1: Distribution of Standardized Predictor Variables with Density Curves

Source: Authors' computation using RStudio

The four predictor variables (RADI, TMAX, TMIN, WINS) in Figure 1, show varied distributional patterns based on their density plots and histograms. TMIN is approximately normal, while TMAX and WINS exhibit slight right skewness, and RADI appears slightly bimodal with a sharp center peak. RADI and WINS also show signs of leptokurtosis, suggesting potential outliers or clustering. However, robust modeling such as Random Forest, Support Vector Regression therefore may improve results for skewed or non-normal predictors.

4.2 Correlation Plot

Figure 2: Pairwise Correlation Plot

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

The pairwise correlation plot of the variables TMIN, TMAX, RAD, WINS, and EVPI is provided in Figure 2 and includes a combination of scatterplots and Pearson correlation coefficients. TMIN and WINS are thought to be the most correlated ($r = 0.517$) with a moderate positive relationship, whereas the rest of the relationships like TMAX-EVPI ($r = 0.281$) and RAD-WINS ($r = -0.301$) are weakly correlated. The rest of the remaining associations are insignificant. The diagonal histograms indicate that TMIN, TMAX, RAD and WINS are almost homogenized and symmetrically distributed whilst EVPI is somewhat skewed with unimodal distribution. Therefore, EVPI indicate a poor simple linear regression in this case which might not be significantly effective, so nonlinear interaction effects would enhance predictive power more consistently.

Table 1: Model Performance Metrics

Model	RMSE	MAPE
MLR	0.03435	0.01978
RF	0.03338	0.01922
SVR_Linear	0.03095	0.01786
SVR_Poly	0.03260	0.01877
SVR_Radial	0.02852	0.01640

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

Table 1 is a comparison of five predictive models based on Root Mean Square error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Percentage error (MAPE). The SVR-Radial is superior to all the models in terms of RMSE (0.0285) and MAPE (0.0164) which show a high predictive accuracy. The SVR-Linear and SVR-Poly are also better in comparison to the traditional MLR and RF models. Although it is simple, the error measures of MLR are the largest implying that it might not be able to effectively capture patterns underlying. Therefore, **nonlinear SVR models** that use the radial kernel have the highest predictive performance.

Figure 3: Time Series Comparison of MAPE Across Predictive Models

Figure 4: Time Series Comparison of RMSE Across Predictive Models

Source: Authors' computation using RStudio

Figure 3 and figure 4 show the Mean Absolute Percentage error (MAPE) and the Root Mean Square error (RMSE) of 5 predictive models; MLR, RF, SVR-Linear, SVR-Poly and SVR-Radial. Higher values of MAPE and RMSE can be statistically considered to be more predictive. In both measures, SVR-Poly and SVR-Radial show the lowest and the most stable error values throughout the time, which implies a better and strong forecasting ability. Instead, MLR shows maximum variability and multiple error spikes especially around meaning inconsistent and less accurate prediction. RF and SVR-Linear have moderate performance but visible though not as strong variations. Therefore, SVR-Poly and SVR-Radial are the most statistically dependable models, which combine accuracy and temporal stability in both the measures of error.

Figure 5: Boxplot of MAPE Distribution Across Predictive Models

Figure 6: Boxplot of RMSE Distribution Across Predictive Models

Source: Authors' computation using RStudio

Figure 5 and figure 6 provide an insight into the predictive accuracy and consistency of five predictive models the distributions of the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) are presented in the boxplot respectively. All models have similar median MAPE values around the same value, statistical evidence of which shows that SVR-Radial shows the lowest and most consistent MAPE, which means improved and stable performance. RF and SVR have slightly broader ranges of MAPE interquartile ranges, indicating higher variability and MLR has a moderate central tendency and dispersion. As far as RMSE is concerned, SVR-Radial shows the best performance, as it has the lowest median and tightest distribution, which indicates a good and reliable result. The median is followed up

by relatively lower values of SVR-Poly and RF with a smaller variability whereas SVR-Linear has the highest spread of RMSE of the SVR models. MLR has the worst and most inconsistent performance, with the greatest RMSE median and variability, and an outlier. Thus, SVR-Radial is statistically the strongest model in both measures of error.

Figure 7: Observed vs. Predicted EVPI Across Models (1995–2023)

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

The scatter plot in figure 7 demonstrates the comparison of the observed and predicted EVPI values of five predictive models; MLR, RF, SVR-Linear, SVR-Poly, and SVR-Radial with a 45degree reference line to indicate the best possible predictions. The level of correspondence to this line statistically shows the accuracy of the models. SVR-Linear and SVR-Radial display predictions that are very close to the ideal line which implies a high accuracy of prediction and generalization. However, MLR and RF are more widely spread across the line, especially at the ends of the distributions, which means that they have systematic over- and under-predictions. SVR-Poly is moderate in terms of fit and more likely to underestimate high EVPI values. Therefore, SVR-Linear and SVR-Radial are more accurate and reliable than the other models in predictions at the time range.

Figure 8: Combined Observed vs. Predicted EVPI Scatter Plot Across All Models (1995–2023)

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

Figure 8 below is a scatterplot that shows the observed and predicted values of EVPI in 1995-2023 using all five of the models; MLR (red), RF (olive), SVR-Linear (cyan), SVR-Poly (blue), and SVR-Radial (magenta) in one plot with the diagonal dashed line indicating an ideal prediction. Proper models should in statistics yield points near to this line. Overall trend indicates that most predictions are above the line in general on all models they tend to over

predict EVPI. The SVR-Linear and SVR-Radial are the ones that cluster closer to the diagonal implying the high predictive accuracy in comparison to the other models. On the contrary, MLR and RF exhibit more dispersion, especially on lower EVPI levels, and frequent over-estimates. Although certain models show better fit, none of them has a better fit in the entire range, particularly in the lower observed value range.

Figure 9: Absolute Prediction Errors Over Time

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

This graph represented in figure 9 illustrates the prediction errors of five models, MLR (Multiple Linear Regression), RF (Random Forest), three Support vector regression models (SVR-Linear, SVR-Poly, SVR-Radial), over time. Statistically, it can be seen that all models possess a general tendency of rising error in the period between early 2000s and around 2007 and then a decline and a leveling off of errors in the period up to about 2015. The models developed after 2015 have a significant upward trend in the prediction error, which might indicate that they are less resilient to updated data. Overall, SVR-Radial has demonstrated the lowest and most consistent error rates over the years, which demonstrates higher generalization performance, whereas MLR and RF exhibit more variation and higher error rates over the last few years, which may be due to overfitting or changes in the data.

Figure 10: Residual Diagnostic Plot

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

The figure 10 residual diagnostic plot indicates the difference between observed and predicted EVPI values (residuals) of the five models (MLR, RF, SVR-Linear, SVR-Poly, and SVR-Radial). Statistically, all the models have residuals that are close to zero meaning the predictions are usually unbiased with no steadfastly over or underestimation. Nevertheless, spikes to a certain extent, notably at the beginning of the 2000s, and 2020, indicate the

occurrence of relatively huge errors in prediction. The models all tend to share a similar pattern of residues over time meaning that they are all reacting to similar trends in the data or noise. Homoscedasticity of the residues is approximately the same and does not seem to have a detectable trend or autocorrelation and so possibly model assumptions on the independence of the residuals and their stability as time passes are possibly acceptable.

Figure 11: Residual Diagnostic Plot with Confidence Bands

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

The figure of 11, residual diagnostic plot, with confidence bands, indicates the residual of five models (MLR, RF, SVR-Linear, SVR-Poly, SVR-Radial) and results with shaded confidence intervals to show acceptable error intervals. Most of the residuals lie within the bands of confidence indicating that most prediction errors are expected to be within the expected limits and no solid indication that models have systematic bias. The residual values are distributed around the zero and are equally distributed over time across the models, which means that they provide equal performance and autocorrelation over time is not apparent. The confidence bands also assist in viewing the models or years with more uncertainty with few cases where the residuals are close to the confidence limits or even above them. This confirms the conclusion that all the models have quite reasonable and stable predictions in the long-term. Therefore, the most suitable model is SVR-Radial, which has high accuracy, the lowest variation in errors, and statistical power throughout the series.

Table 2: Ljung-Box Test Results

Model	p-value
MLR	0.169
RF	0.170
SVR_Linear	0.302
SVR_Poly	0.129
SVR_Radial	0.224

Source: Authors’ computation using RStudio

Table 2 of the Ljung-Box test results indicate that the five models, which are MLR, RF, SVR-Linear, SVR-Poly and SVR-Radial, have a p-value greater than 0.05 therefore denoting the

absence of any significant autocorrelation in their residuals and hence fulfilling the assumption of residual independence. The evidence of independence is the highest in SVR-Linear and the p-value stands at 0.302, closely followed by SVR-Radial standing at 0.224 implying that both the models are highly independent with a strong temporal stability. MLR and RF are moderate with p-values of about 0.17 with SVR-Poly the weakest with the lowest p-value of 0.129. Taking into account these findings in addition to the previous performance studies especially the low and steady prediction errors of SVR-Radial, it can be concluded that SVR-Radial is the most statistically sound and accurate model and SVR-Linear is a good alternative as it has high residual independence. In this research, the lowest RMSE and MAPE were achieved with SVR-RBF, which is able to capture non-linear relationships in solar irradiance data and evaporation data as compared to MLR or Random Forest. The competitive behavior of SVR-linear models further validates the fact that the ML methods are also able to maintain independence of residual values and at the same time strike a balance between computational efficiency. Linear models and Random Forest performed poorly, in line with the findings by Nwanze et al. (2024) and Ikemba et al. (2024), because they have low ability to capture complex patterns over time. In this way, the reviewed literature justifies the use of nonlinear statistical learning tools in the solar energy prediction in Nigeria and supports the policy implications of water resource management, introduction of renewable energy sources, and climate adaptation policies.

5 CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper performed a thorough comparative evaluation of five statistical learning models, Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR), random forest (RF), Support Vector Regression (SVR) with linear, polynomial and radial kernels, to predict solar irradiance using the long-term EVPI data in Nigeria. As the results indicate, there were evident performance differences between the models: the SVR using a radial basis function (RBF) kernel always yielded the lowest RMSE and MAPE values, its performance was more accurate, stable, and robust in all diagnostic assessments. The SVR linear kernel was predicting fairly well, albeit with a little more error variance, whereas the MLR and RF models demonstrated little predictive power because they failed to describe nonlinear relationships that exist between climatic variables. The SVR poly kernel had average accuracy though it had less stable residual behavior. These findings are corroborated by other studies by the same research question in other areas, including Bargam et al. (2024) in Morocco and Nguyen et al. (2025), which also point to nonlinear learning models as the predominant models in climate and hydro meteorological predictions. In sum, the research comes to the conclusion that nonlinear models, especially the SVR-RBF provides the most stable and accurate model of solar irradiance prediction in Nigeria, which has significant implications to solar evaporation analysis, water resource planning and sustainable energy planning.

There is a number of specific recommendations, pursuing which the policy action and the reinforcement of renewable energy planning in Nigeria are based, based on these findings. To start with, the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMeT) ought to improve national weather data infrastructure by increasing the number of the weather monitoring stations, their reliability, and automation as nonlinear models depend strongly on the quality of datasets. Second, the Federal Ministry of Power and the Rural Electrification Agency (REA) is advised to incorporate SVR-RBF forecasting tools in the feasibility analysis of mini-grids, off grid systems, and large-scale solar installations to decrease production uncertainties and enhance the reliability of underserved regions. Third, Federal Ministry of Water Resources ought to integrate solar irradiance projections produced by SVR-RBF into evaporation modelling, irrigation planning and dam operation structures, especially in the drought prone north. Fourth, it is recommended that the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN) should design a country-

wide machine-learning-based forecasting system of renewable energy that institutionalizes the application of developed predictive models, as is the world best practice in developing economies. Fifth, these predictive tools should be incorporated into climate change adaptation strategies and policies on environmental sustainability by the Ministry of Environment and Climate Change to guide drought reduction and land reclamation measures and clean energy transition policies. Moreover, nonlinear predictive tools, particularly SVR-RBF, should be given priority by state governments and developers of renewable energy during site selection process, design of the project and during investment planning to ensure that there is less monetary risk and more energy output. Lastly, training and research on climate-oriented machine learning should be encouraged in academic and research institutions as a way of developing national technical capacity. Generally, these suggestions point to the possibility of the beneficial impact of advanced statistical learning models on the transformation of renewable energy planning, environmental management, and climate adaptation activities in Nigeria, which will contribute to more robust and data-driven decision-making in key areas.

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